

OntoFoCE and ObE Forensics. Email-traceability supporting tools for Digital Forensics
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Supplementary material: OntoFoCE Validation (Scenario 2)

OntoFoCE has been tested in terms of the representativeness of the ontological model developed, considering the characteristics of the language used. With the auxiliary tools of the Protégé environment (Hermit reasoner 1.3.8.413), the initial consistency checks of OntoFoCE's OWL model were performed, using an instantiation test bench with three different scenarios for the analysis of emails: 1) the forensic analysis of a single email; 2) the analysis of an email sent to several recipients, and 3) the analysis of a set of email accounts with a certain number of emails in each. These three scenarios are furtherly described in section 3.5 of [Parra, 2019] and shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: The 3 scenarios used for OntoFoCE validation

In this document, information about Scenario 2 is presented. Fig.2 shows a screenshot of the analyzed email.

Figure 2: Email analyzed in scenario 2

This email was sent from bgallo@ucasal.edu.ar to three users identified with the recipient accounts enzo.notario@gmail.com, luzbibianaclara@gmail.com and erivetti83@gmail.com. Following the indicated procedure, the expert extracts the corresponding headers from the three recipient accounts. Fig. 3 to Fig. 5 show these headers. In each figure, the data of interest has been highlighted. In order to focus on the header data relevant to the expert analysis, some sections of the header referring to irrelevant parameters have been omitted. For simplicity, the occurrences are labeled with the acronym SO for the sending occurrence, TO..n for the transmission occurrences and RO for the receiving occurrence.

Figure 3: HEADER_R1 - Header of the email received in the account: enzo.notario@gmail.com

Figure 4: HEADER_R2 -Header of the email received in the account: erivetti83@gmail.com

attribute, in which case the occurrence is marked as ORIGINAL. If the identifier was found in the *from* sub-attribute, the occurrence is labeled as GENERATED.

Table 1: Occurrences identified in each Received Line of the HEADER_R3 header

LINE	From/by	DATE	OCCURRENCE	DESCRIPTION OF THE DEVICE	TYPE OF OCCURRENCE
A	2002:a2e:658d::	2018-07-08 T15:41:46	EO	DEVICE_E2	ORIGINAL
B	mail-lj1-f180.google.com	2018-07-08 T15:41:48	TO1	SERVER_1	ORIGINAL
C	209.85.208.170	2018-07-08 T15:41:48	TO2	SERVER_2	GENERATED
	mail.ucasal.edu.ar	2018-07-08 T15:41:48	TO3	SERVER_3	ORIGINAL
D	127.0.0.1	2018-07-08 T15:41:51	TO4	SERVER_4	GENERATED
	127.0.0.1	2018-07-08 T15:41:51	TO5	SERVER_4	ORIGINAL
E	127.0.0.1	2018-07-08 T15:41:52	TO6	SERVER_4	GENERATED
	mail.ucasal.edu.ar	2018-07-08 T15:41:52	TO7	SERVER_3	ORIGINAL
F	200.10.180.145	2018-07-08 T15:41:52	TO8	SERVER_5	GENERATED
	mail.ucasal.edu.ar	2018-07-08 T15:41:52	TO9	SERVER_3	ORIGINAL
G	127.0.0.1	2018-07-08 T15:41:52	TO10	SERVER_4	GENERATED
	127.0.0.1	2018-07-08 T15:41:52	TO11	SERVER_4	ORIGINAL
H	127.0.0.1	2018-07-08 T15:41:52	TO12	SERVER_4	GENERATED
	127.0.0.1	2018-07-08 T15:41:52	TO13	SERVER_4	ORIGINAL
I	200.10.181.3	2018-07-08 T15:41:54	TO14	SERVER_6	GENERATED
	ismtpd0004pliad1.sendgrid.net	2018-07-08 T15:41:54	TO15	SERVER_7	ORIGINAL
J	filter0071p3mdw1.sendgrid.net	2018-07-08 T15:41:55	TO16	SERVER_8	ORIGINAL
K	168.245.62.79	2018-07-08 T15:41:58	TO17	SERVER_9	GENERATED
	mx.google.com	2018-07-08 T15:41:58	TO18	SERVER_10	ORIGINAL
L	2002:ac8:5207:	2018-07-08 T15:41:58	TO19	SERVER_11	ORIGINAL
M	2002:a4a:d4d5:0:0:0:0:0	2018-07-08 T15:41:59	RO	DEVICE_R3	ORIGINAL

It is possible to access the OWL implementation of this scenario at https://obe.digilab.ucasal.edu.ar/owl_escenario_2/. The following figures show the results of the answers to some competency questions using scenario 2.

SPARQL query:

```

PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
PREFIX oc: <http://www.semanticweb.org/beatr/ontologies/2018/0/ontologia_correos#>
SELECT DISTINCT ?correo ?asunto ?fechaEmision ?nombreCuentaReceptor
WHERE {
  ?cuenta oc:cuentaEmisorEmiteCorreo ?correo.
  ?cuentaRep oc:cuentaReceptorRecibeCorreo ?correo.
  ?cuentaRep oc:cuentaCorreo ?nombreCuentaReceptor.
  ?correo oc:correoTieneSecuencia ?s.
  ?s oc:secuenciaTieneHilo ?h.
  ?h oc:hiloTieneOcurrencia ?o.
  ?o oc:ocurrenciaTieneAsunto ?a.
  ?a oc:contenidoAsunto ?asunto.
  ?o rdf:type oc:OcurrenciaDeEmision.
  ?o oc:fechaHoraOcurrencia ?fechaEmision.
  FILTER (?cuenta=oc:CUENTA_E1)}

```

correo	asunto	fechaEmision	nombreCuentaReceptor
C1	"Colaboración en investigación"	"2018-07-08T15:41:46" <small><http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#dateTime></small>	"luzbibianaclara"@gmail.com
C1	"Colaboración en investigación"	"2018-07-08T15:41:46" <small><http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#dateTime></small>	"Enzo Notario"
C1	"Colaboración en investigación"	"2018-07-08T15:41:46" <small><http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#dateTime></small>	"erivetti83"@gmail.com

Figure 6: CQ10: Given an account A, what emails did it send?

SPARQL query:	
<pre> PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> PREFIX oc: <http://www.semanticweb.org/beatr/ontologies/2018/0/ontologia_correos#> SELECT ?direccion ?localizacion WHERE { ?IP oc:geoLocalizacionIP ?localizacion. ?IP oc:identificadorEquipo ?direccion. FILTER (?IP=oc:ID_S2). } </pre>	
direccion	localizacion
"209.85.208.170"	"Latitud 39.0438 Longitud -77.4874"

Figure 7: CQ14: Given an IP address, what is its geographic location?

SPARQL query:	
<pre> PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> PREFIX oc: <http://www.semanticweb.org/beatr/ontologies/2018/0/ontologia_correos#> SELECT DISTINCT ?equipo ?Cabecera WHERE { ?equipo oc:equipoTieneld ?IP. ?ocurrencia oc:ocurrenciaResideEnEquipo ?equipo. ?hilo oc:hiloTieneOcurrencia ?ocurrencia. ?s oc:secuenciaTieneHilo ?hilo. ?correo oc:correoTieneSecuencia ?s. ?e oc:cuentaEmisorEmiteCorreo ?correo. ?IP oc:identificadorEquipo ?direccion. ?ocurrencia oc:ocurrenciaTieneCabecera ?Cabecera. FILTER regex(?direccion,"209.85.208.170").} </pre>	
equipo	
SERVIDOR_2	CABECERA_R3
SERVIDOR_2	CABECERA_R1
SERVIDOR_2	CABECERA_R2

Figure 8: CQ15: What emails traveled through the device that has a given IP?

Testing Obe Forensics using scenario 2.

Once the email has been processed, the expert has to identify the competency questions that will allow them to answer the EISTEEs. Thus, for each of these, the necessary competency questions are processed. It is possible to generate the

TECHNICAL EXPERT REPORT (Figure 9 to Figure 11) using the corresponding option on the ObE Forensics main screen. For the example analyzed, email C1 is selected on the navigation panel on the left, competency questions CQ10, CQ14 and CQ15 are selected on the navigation panel in the center, and the application shows the preview of the report obtained.

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ObE Forensics

RESULTADO DE LA PREGUNTA DE COMPETENCIA N° 10

Correos electrónicos enviados por bgallo@ucasal.edu.ar
Total: 3 E-mails

1° E-mail

Asunto: **Colaboracion en investigacion**

ID: <CAH18OQUiLqm+iDyLJkrHg9kOto2PRDR4AG3mp1RAQDCwD2JccA@mail.gmail.com>

Fecha: 2018-07-08T12:41:56-03:00

Emisor	Receptor
Ing. H. Beatriz P. de Gallo bgallo@ucasal.edu.ar	Enzo Notario enzo.notario@gmail.com

2° E-mail

Asunto: **Colaboración en investigación**

ID: <CAH18OQUiLqm+iDyLJkrHg9kOto2PRDR4AG3mp1RAQDCwD2JccA@mail.gmail.com>

Fecha: 2018-07-08T12:41:56-03:00

Emisor	Receptor
Ing. H. Beatriz P. de Gallo bgallo@ucasal.edu.ar	Esteban Rivetti erivetti83@gmail.com

3° E-mail

Asunto: **Colaboración en investigación**

ID: <CAH18OQUiLqm+iDyLJkrHg9kOto2PRDR4AG3mp1RAQDCwD2JccA@mail.gmail.com>

Fecha: 2018-07-08T12:41:56-03:00

Emisor	Receptor
Ing. H. Beatriz P. de Gallo bgallo@ucasal.edu.ar	luz bibiana Clara luzbibianaclara@gmail.com

Figure 9: Technical Expert Report for CQ10

ObE Forensics

RESULTADO DE LA PREGUNTA DE COMPETENCIA N° 14

Geolocalización de la IP mail-lj1-f170.google.co

IP 181.91.147.216
Código ISO US
País United States
Ciudad New Haven
Abrev. Provincia/Estado CT
Provincia/Estado Connecticut
Código postal 06510
Latitud 41.31
Longitud -72.92
Zona horaria America/New_York
Continente NA
Moneda USD

Figure 10: Technical Expert Report for CQ14

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ObE Forensics

RESULTADO DE LA PREGUNTA DE COMPETENCIA N° 15

Correos electrónicos que han pasado por la IP 209.85.208.170

Total: **3 E-mails**

1° E-mail

Asunto: **Colaboracion en investigacion**

ID: <CAH18OQUiLqm+iDyLJkrHg9kOto2PRDR4AG3mp1RAQDCwD2JccA@mail.gmail.com>

Fecha: **2018-07-08T12:41:56-03:00**

<p style="font-size: x-small; margin: 0;">Emisor</p> <div style="border: 1px solid gray; padding: 5px; margin-top: 5px;"> <p style="margin: 0;">Ing. H. Beatriz P. de Gallo bgallo@ucasal.edu.ar</p> </div>	<p style="font-size: x-small; margin: 0;">Receptor</p> <div style="border: 1px solid gray; padding: 5px; margin-top: 5px;"> <p style="margin: 0;">Enzo Notario enzo.notario@gmail.com</p> </div>
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ObE Forensics

2° E-mail

Asunto: **Colaboración en investigación**

ID: <CAH18OQUiLqm+iDyLJkrHg9kOto2PRDR4AG3mp1RAQDCwD2JccA@mail.gmail.com>

Fecha: **2018-07-08T12:41:56-03:00**

<p style="font-size: x-small; margin: 0;">Emisor</p> <div style="border: 1px solid gray; padding: 5px; margin-top: 5px;"> <p style="margin: 0;">Ing. H. Beatriz P. de Gallo bgallo@ucasal.edu.ar</p> </div>	<p style="font-size: x-small; margin: 0;">Receptor</p> <div style="border: 1px solid gray; padding: 5px; margin-top: 5px;"> <p style="margin: 0;">Esteban Rivetti erivetti83@gmail.com</p> </div>
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ObE Forensics

3° E-mail

Asunto: **Colaboración en investigación**

ID: <CAH18OQUiLqm+iDyLJkrHg9kOto2PRDR4AG3mp1RAQDCwD2JccA@mail.gmail.com>

Fecha: **2018-07-08T12:41:56-03:00**

<p style="font-size: x-small; margin: 0;">Emisor</p> <div style="border: 1px solid gray; padding: 5px; margin-top: 5px;"> <p style="margin: 0;">Ing. H. Beatriz P. de Gallo bgallo@ucasal.edu.ar</p> </div>	<p style="font-size: x-small; margin: 0;">Receptor</p> <div style="border: 1px solid gray; padding: 5px; margin-top: 5px;"> <p style="margin: 0;">luz bibiana Clara luzbibianaclara@gmail.com</p> </div>
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Figure 11: Technical Expert Report for CQ15

REFERENCES:

Parra, H. B. (2019). *Una Ontología del Correo Electrónico y su Trazabilidad como Soporte para la Forensia Digital* [Universidad Tecnológica Nacional]. <https://digilab.ucasal.edu.ar/tesis>